

STRESS INTENSITIES AT THE INTERFACE CORNER OF CO-CURED LAP JOINTS

Kum Cheol Shin¹, Won Seok Kim¹, and Jung Ju Lee¹

¹*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology
373-1, Yusong-dong, Yuseong-gu, Daejeon, Korea(south)*

SUMMARY: Co-cured lap joints are of interest in some engineering fields. For analyzing the failure at the interface of the co-cured lap joint, it is important to investigate stress intensities at the interface corner. In this paper, the eigenvalue problem of a bonded structure with anisotropic and isotropic adherends is considered to determine eigenvalues and eigenvectors and thereafter get asymptotic stress and displacement fields near the interface through the expanded Stroh formalism. In order to obtain stress intensities at the interface corner H-integral, which is derived from the Betti's reciprocal principle, is used. For helping understand the procedure an example of a co-cured double lap joint with composite and steel adherends is presented. Finally how to get stress intensities at the interface corner is explained in detail and the design method of co-cured lap joints is presented.

KEYWORDS: stress intensities, co-cured lap joints, interface corner, H-integral.

INTRODUCTION

A co-cured joint is a kind of the adhesively bonded joint of using an adhesive to bond two or more adherends. However, it is different from the adhesively bonded joint in a manufacturing process point of view. It is fabricated by using excess resin extracted from the composite material during the curing process. Therefore, the manufacturing process of the co-cured joint is simpler than that of the adhesively bonded joint because it requires no surface treatment of the composite adherend and the bonding process can be performed simultaneously during the curing process [1].

Since the first report on mechanical properties of the co-cured joint was issued in the middle of 1990s, some researchers have introduced some manufacturing processes and mechanical characteristics of the co-cured composite-composite joint [2-6]. Most of the papers used the stress analysis method, which often depends on the number of meshes when using the finite element analysis, for prediction of failure of the co-cured lap joints. Because of the stress concentration at the interface corner it would be better to consider stress intensities for prediction of tensile load bearing capacity. The use of a critical value of the stress intensities in linear elastic fracture mechanics is quite mature. Therefore, many researchers have tried to calculate stress intensities of bonded joints.

Muskhelishvili [7] developed the two-dimensional isotropic elasticity theory with complex variables and Lekhnitskii [8], Eshelby *et al.* [9], and Stroh [10] formulated the anisotropic elasticity one. Suo [11-12] gave solutions for the isotropic bi-material problem and the

anisotropic bi-material problem, respectively. Choi [13] expanded the Stroh formalism of the anisotropic elasticity into the anisotropic/isotropic elasticity problem with a crack.

The Reciprocal Work Contour Integral Method (RWCIM) is one of the most powerful approaches of using finite element results to obtain stress intensities of configurations with cracks or notches. Some researchers used the RWCIM to yield stress intensities of the interface corner of bi-materials with cracks or notches [14-18].

In this paper, a simple method to obtain stress intensities at the interface corners of anisotropic and isotropic adherends with a notch was introduced. For getting stress singularities at the interface corner of anisotropic/isotropic bi-materials the expanded Stroh formalism was used. The formalism was also used to obtain eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors of anisotropic/isotropic bi-materials. Complex eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors, not treated by any other researchers for the expanded Stroh formalism, were considered. An example of the co-cured double lap joint with composite and steel adherends was presented to help readers understand the procedure. A general solution for the displacement field of the isotropic material was appended to the expanded Stroh formalism through an original idea. Using the stress singularity complimentary stress and displacement fields were determined. Finally stress intensities at the interface corner of anisotropic/isotropic bi-materials were explicitly given using the H-integral, the Reciprocal Work Contour Integral Method.

LINEAR ELASTICITY FOR 2D DEFORMATION

For investigating the behavior at the interface corner of bonded joints, consider the bi-material interface corner shown in Fig. 1. Upper and lower interface corner flanks are $\theta = \alpha$ and $\theta = -\beta$ where the angle θ is measured from the interface. The solid is composed of two materials denoted by A and B which are perfectly bonded along $\theta = 0$. A- and B-materials are anisotropic and isotropic materials, respectively. The interface corner flanks are traction free and the solid is loaded at remote boundaries by tractions or displacements.

Fig. 1: Geometry of the bonded joint

Anisotropic Elasticity

Referring to a fixed rectangular coordinate system x_i ($i=1, 2, 3$), let σ_{ij} , u_i , and ε_{ij} be the stress, displacement, and strain, respectively, in an anisotropic elastic material. The stress-strain law can be written as

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sum_{k,s=1}^3 C_{ijks} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_s} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (2)$$

where C_{ijks} are the elastic stiffnesses which are components of a fourth rank tensor. The equation of equilibrium is

$$\sum_{j,k,s=1}^3 C_{ijks} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_j \partial x_s} = 0. \quad (3)$$

For two-dimensional deformations in which u_i ($i=1, 2, 3$) depends on x_1 and x_2 only, Eq. (3) is a homogenous second-order differential equation in two independent variables x_1 and x_2 . A general solution for u_i depends on one composite variable that is a linear combination of x_1 and x_2 . Without loss in generality we choose the coefficient of x_1 in the linear combination to be unity and let

$$\{u_i\} = 2\text{Re}[\mathbf{A}\mathbf{f}(z)] \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{f}(z) = [f_1(z_1), f_2(z_2), f_3(z_3)]^T. \quad (5)$$

The superscript T denotes the transpose and $z = x_1 + px_2$. Each column of \mathbf{A} and p are the eigenvector and the eigenvalue with positive imaginary part, respectively, to be determined. A general solution for the displacements satisfying Eq. (3) and the corresponding stresses may be written as [9-10]

$$\left\{ \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1} \right\} = 2\text{Re}[\mathbf{A}\mathbf{f}'(z)] \quad (6)$$

$$\{\sigma_{2i}\} = 2\text{Re}[\mathbf{B}\mathbf{f}'(z)] \quad (7)$$

$$\{\sigma_{1i}\} = 2\text{Re}[\mathbf{D}\mathbf{f}'(z)] \quad (8)$$

Here, ($'$) is designated as the derivative with respect to the associated arguments. Differentiation twice of Eq. (4) with x gives the sextic equation of

$$\sum_{k=1}^3 [C_{i1k1} + p_\alpha (C_{i1k2} + C_{i2k1}) + p_\alpha^2 C_{i2k2}] A_{ka} = 0. \quad (9)$$

This can be written in matrix notation as

$$\{\mathbf{Q} + p(\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{R}^T) + p^2\mathbf{T}\}\mathbf{A} = 0 \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{R} , and \mathbf{T} are 3×3 matrices whose components are

$$Q_{ik} = C_{i1k1} \quad R_{ik} = C_{i1k2} \quad T_{ik} = C_{i2k2}. \quad (11)$$

It is seen that \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{T} are symmetric and positive definite if the strain energy is positive. Employing the contracted notation for C_{ijks} the three matrices \mathbf{Q} , \mathbf{R} , and \mathbf{T} have the expressions

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{16} & C_{15} \\ C_{16} & C_{66} & C_{56} \\ C_{15} & C_{56} & C_{55} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{R} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{16} & C_{12} & C_{14} \\ C_{66} & C_{26} & C_{46} \\ C_{56} & C_{25} & C_{45} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{66} & C_{26} & C_{46} \\ C_{26} & C_{22} & C_{24} \\ C_{46} & C_{24} & C_{44} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

For a nontrivial solution of \mathbf{A} we must have

$$|\mathbf{Q} + p(\mathbf{R} + \mathbf{R}^T) + p^2\mathbf{T}| = 0 \quad (13)$$

which gives six roots for the eigenvalue p . The associated eigenvector matrix \mathbf{A} is determined from Eq. (9). Matrices \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} in Eqs. (7) and (8) are given by

$$B_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^3 (C_{i2k1} + p_j C_{i2k2}) A_{kj} \quad (14)$$

and

$$D_{ij} = -B_{ij} p_j \quad (\text{not sum over } j). \quad (15)$$

In order to avoid confusion, no summation is assumed implicitly for repeated indices in this paper. If Eq. (9) has three distinct pairs of complex roots on which we are concentrating, the matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are non-singular.

For the asymptotic analysis of the stress state near the bi-material interface corner, we assume a solution of the form [19]:

$$\mathbf{f}(z) = \frac{1}{\lambda} z^\lambda \mathbf{q}. \quad (19)$$

$$z_\alpha = x_1 + p_\alpha x_2 = r(\cos\theta + p_\alpha \sin\theta) = r\zeta_\alpha(\theta). \quad (20)$$

The complete solution for the displacement vector, the stress function, and the traction vector of the anisotropic adherend is then:

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{1}{\lambda} z^\lambda \mathbf{A}\mathbf{q} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \bar{z}^{\bar{\lambda}} \overline{\mathbf{A}\mathbf{q}} \quad (21)$$

$$\phi = \frac{1}{\lambda} z^\lambda \mathbf{B}\mathbf{q} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \bar{z}^{\bar{\lambda}} \overline{\mathbf{B}\mathbf{q}}. \quad (22)$$

\mathbf{q} is a vector of constants to be determined.

Isotropic Elasticity

The components of the stresses and displacements for an isotropic body under plane deformation are expressed in terms of Muskhelishvili complex potentials for in-plane and anti-plane problems as follows [1, 20]:

$$\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} = 2[\Phi(z) + \overline{\Phi(z)}] \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_{22} + i\sigma_{12} = \overline{\Phi(z)} + \Omega(z) + (\bar{z} - z)\Phi'(z) \quad (24)$$

$$\sigma_{32} + i\sigma_{31} = \omega(z) \quad (25)$$

$$-2iG \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} (u_2 + iu_1) = \kappa \overline{\Phi(z)} - \Omega(z) - (\bar{z} - z)\Phi'(z) \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial x_1} = \frac{1}{2Gi} [\omega(z) - \overline{\omega(z)}] \quad (27)$$

where $\kappa = 3 - 4\nu$ for plane strain and $\kappa = (3 - \nu)/(1 + \nu)$ for plane stress, ν and G are Poisson's ratio and shear modulus, respectively. With a view to relate the potentials $\Phi(z)$, $\Omega(z)$ and $\omega(z)$ in Eqs. (23)-(27) with $\mathbf{f}'(z)$ in Eqs. (5)-(8), we rewrite Eqs. (23)-(27) as follows [13]:

$$\left\{ \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_1} \right\} = 2 \operatorname{Re}[\mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{g}'(z)] \quad (28)$$

$$\{\sigma_{2i}\} = 2 \operatorname{Re}[\mathbf{B}^* \mathbf{g}'(z)] \quad (29)$$

$$\{\sigma_{ii}\} = 2 \operatorname{Re}[\mathbf{D}^* \mathbf{g}'(z)] \quad (30)$$

where

$$\mathbf{g}'(z) = [\Phi(z), \Omega(z) + (\bar{z} - z)\Phi'(z), \omega(z)]^T = \mathbf{f}'^*(z) + (\bar{z} - z)\mathbf{Q}^* \cdot \mathbf{f}''^*(z) \quad (31)$$

$$\mathbf{f}'^*(z) = [\Phi(z), \Omega(z), \omega(z)]^T \quad (32)$$

$$\mathbf{A}^* = \frac{1}{4Gi} \begin{bmatrix} \kappa i & -i & 0 \\ \kappa & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{B}^* = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} i & -i & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{D}^* = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & -1 & 0 \\ i & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{Q}^* = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (33)-(36)$$

Expanding the above equation using the Muskhelishvili complex potentials gives the solution for the displacement of the isotropic material

$$\{u_i\} = 2 \operatorname{Re}[\mathbf{A}^* \mathbf{g}(z)] \quad (37)$$

$$\mathbf{g}(z) = \mathbf{f}^*(z) + (\bar{z} - z)\mathbf{Q}^* \cdot \mathbf{f}'^*(z). \quad (38)$$

According to the equivalence theorem [13], the matrices \mathbf{A}^* , \mathbf{B}^* , \mathbf{D}^* , and $\mathbf{f}'^*(z)$ for an isotropic material correspond to \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{D} , and $\mathbf{f}(z)$ for an anisotropic material, respectively.

EXAMPLE OF THE CO-CURED DOUBLE LAP JOINT

For helping readers understand the eigenvector approach to calculate eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors, consider an example, namely a notch problem of the co-cured double lap joint with composite and steel adherends. Fig. 2 shows geometries of the example studied in this paper. The notch is composed of an anisotropic material with $\alpha = 180^\circ$ and an isotropic material with $\beta = 90^\circ$. Boundary conditions along the interface are

$$\mathbf{u}^A(0) = \mathbf{u}^B(0) \quad (39)$$

$$\mathbf{t}^A(0) = \mathbf{t}^B(0). \quad (40)$$

Applying the boundary conditions, we can obtain two tensor equations equal to

$$\frac{1}{\lambda} r^\lambda \mathbf{A}^A \mathbf{q}^A + \frac{1}{\bar{\lambda}} r^{\bar{\lambda}} \overline{\mathbf{A}^A \mathbf{q}^A} = \frac{1}{\lambda} r^\lambda \mathbf{A}^B \mathbf{q}^B + \frac{1}{\bar{\lambda}} r^{\bar{\lambda}} \overline{\mathbf{A}^B \mathbf{q}^B} \quad (41)$$

$$r^{\lambda-1} \mathbf{B}^A \mathbf{q}^A + r^{\bar{\lambda}-1} \overline{\mathbf{B}^A \mathbf{q}^A} = r^{\lambda-1} \mathbf{B}^B \mathbf{q}^B + r^{\bar{\lambda}-1} \overline{\mathbf{B}^B \mathbf{q}^B}. \quad (42)$$

Fig. 2: Co-cured double lap joint with a notch ($\alpha=180^\circ$ and $\beta=90^\circ$) (a) shape of the specimen and (b) geometry of the interface corner

Imposing the traction-free requirement on the corner faces yields six homogenous boundary conditions

$$\mathbf{t}^A(\pi) = 0 \quad (43)$$

$$\mathbf{t}^B\left(-\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 0. \quad (44)$$

Applying Eqs. (43) and (44), we can obtain two tensor equations for calculating the stress singularity:

$$r^{\lambda-1} e^{i\pi(\lambda-1)} \mathbf{B}^A \mathbf{q}^A + r^{\bar{\lambda}-1} e^{-i\pi(\bar{\lambda}-1)} \overline{\mathbf{B}^A \mathbf{q}^A} = 0 \quad (45)$$

$$r^{\lambda-1} e^{\frac{\pi}{2}i(\lambda-1)} \mathbf{D}^B \mathbf{V}^B \mathbf{q}^B + r^{\bar{\lambda}-1} e^{\frac{\pi}{2}i(\bar{\lambda}-1)} \overline{\mathbf{D}^B \mathbf{V}^B \mathbf{q}^B} = 0. \quad (46)$$

where $\mathbf{V}^B = \mathbf{I} - 2(\lambda-1)\mathbf{Q}^*$. Applying these boundary conditions yields a set of simultaneous algebraic equations given by

$$\mathbf{K}(\lambda)\mathbf{q}(\lambda) = 0 \quad (47)$$

The vector \mathbf{q} now contains the six components of the \mathbf{q} vectors of materials A and B, i.e. namely $\mathbf{q} = [\mathbf{q}^A \quad \mathbf{q}^B]^T$. $\mathbf{K}(\lambda)$ takes a form as follows:

$$\mathbf{K}(\lambda) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\lambda} \mathbf{A}^A - \frac{1}{\bar{\lambda}} e^{i\pi(\lambda+\bar{\lambda})} \overline{\mathbf{A}^A \mathbf{B}^{A^{-1}} \mathbf{B}^A} & -\frac{1}{\lambda} \mathbf{A}^B - \frac{1}{\bar{\lambda}} e^{-\frac{\pi}{2}i(\lambda+\bar{\lambda})} \overline{\mathbf{A}^B \mathbf{U}^B} \\ \mathbf{B}^A - e^{i\pi(\lambda+\bar{\lambda})} \mathbf{B}^A & -\mathbf{B}^B - e^{-\frac{\pi}{2}i(\lambda+\bar{\lambda})} \overline{\mathbf{B}^B \mathbf{U}^B} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (48)$$

where $\mathbf{U}^B = \overline{\mathbf{V}^B}^{-1} \overline{\mathbf{D}^B}^{-1} \mathbf{D}^B \mathbf{V}^B$. Here, $i = \sqrt{-1}$ and $(\quad)^{-1}$ stands for the inverse of the matrix. For a nontrivial solution to exist we must have

$$\det[\mathbf{K}(\lambda)] = 0. \quad (49)$$

From Eq. (49) we can obtain the stress singularity and the eigenvector \mathbf{q} .

ASYMPTOTIC SINGULAR FIELDS

Since the eigenvectors for each mode are determined only up to an arbitrary constant, we normalize the mode I fields so that $\sigma_{22}(\theta=0) = K_I^n r^{\lambda_I-1}$ and the mode II fields so that $\sigma_{12}(\theta=0) = K_{II}^n r^{\lambda_{II}-1}$. Here we consider complex eigenvalues λ_I and λ_{II} . With these normalizations, the asymptotic singular fields can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{ij}^M = K_I^n r^{\lambda_I-1} \Sigma_{ij}^{I,M}(\theta) + K_{II}^n r^{\lambda_{II}-1} \Sigma_{ij}^{II,M}(\theta) \quad (50)$$

$$u_i^M = K_I^n r^{\lambda_I} \Pi_i^{I,M}(\theta) + K_{II}^n r^{\lambda_{II}} \Pi_i^{II,M}(\theta). \quad (51)$$

where $M=A$ and B , and

$$\Sigma_{iI}^{IA}(\theta) = \mathbf{D}^A \text{diag}[\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_I-1}] \mathbf{q}^{A^I} + \overline{\mathbf{D}^A} \text{diag}\left[\overline{\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_I-1}}\right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{A^I}} \quad (52)$$

$$\Sigma_{2I}^{IA}(\theta) = \mathbf{B}^A \text{diag}[\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_I-1}] \mathbf{q}^{A^I} + \overline{\mathbf{B}^A} \text{diag}\left[\overline{\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_I-1}}\right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{A^I}} \quad (53)$$

$$\Pi_i^{IA}(\theta) = \frac{1}{\lambda_I} \mathbf{A}^A \text{diag}[\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_I}] \mathbf{q}^{A^I} + \frac{1}{\lambda_I} \overline{\mathbf{A}^A} \text{diag}\left[\overline{\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_I}}\right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{A^I}} \quad (54)$$

$$\Sigma_{iI}^{II}(\theta) = \mathbf{D}^A \text{diag}[\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_{II}-1}] \mathbf{q}^{A^{II}} + \overline{\mathbf{D}^A} \text{diag}\left[\overline{\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_{II}-1}}\right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{A^{II}}} \quad (55)$$

$$\Sigma_{2I}^{II}(\theta) = \mathbf{B}^A \text{diag}[\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_{II}-1}] \mathbf{q}^{A^{II}} + \overline{\mathbf{B}^A} \text{diag}\left[\overline{\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_{II}-1}}\right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{A^{II}}} \quad (56)$$

$$\Pi_i^{II}(\theta) = \frac{1}{\lambda_{II}} \mathbf{A}^A \text{diag}[\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_{II}}] \mathbf{q}^{A^{II}} + \frac{1}{\lambda_{II}} \overline{\mathbf{A}^A} \text{diag}\left[\overline{\zeta_\alpha^A(\theta)^{\lambda_{II}}}\right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{A^{II}}} \quad (57)$$

$$\Sigma_{iB}^{IB}(\theta) = e^{i\theta(\lambda_I-1)} \mathbf{D}^B [\mathbf{I} - (\lambda_I - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \mathbf{q}^{B^I} + e^{-i\theta(\overline{\lambda_I}-1)} \overline{\mathbf{D}^B} [\mathbf{I} - (\overline{\lambda_I} - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{B^I}} \quad (58)$$

$$\Sigma_{2I}^{IB}(\theta) = e^{i\theta(\lambda_I-1)} \mathbf{B}^B [\mathbf{I} - (\lambda_I - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \mathbf{q}^{B^I} + e^{-i\theta(\overline{\lambda_I}-1)} \overline{\mathbf{B}^B} [\mathbf{I} - (\overline{\lambda_I} - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{B^I}} \quad (59)$$

$$\Pi_i^{IB}(\theta) = e^{i\theta\lambda_I} \mathbf{A}^B \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_I} \mathbf{I} - (1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^* \right] \mathbf{q}^{B^I} + e^{-i\theta\overline{\lambda_I}} \overline{\mathbf{A}^B} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_I} \mathbf{I} - (1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^* \right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{B^I}} \quad (60)$$

$$\Sigma_{iB}^{II}(\theta) = e^{i\theta(\lambda_{II}-1)} \mathbf{D}^B [\mathbf{I} - (\lambda_{II} - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \mathbf{q}^{B^{II}} + e^{-i\theta(\overline{\lambda_{II}}-1)} \overline{\mathbf{D}^B} [\mathbf{I} - (\overline{\lambda_{II}} - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{B^{II}}} \quad (61)$$

$$\Sigma_{2I}^{II}(\theta) = e^{i\theta(\lambda_{II}-1)} \mathbf{B}^B [\mathbf{I} - (\lambda_{II} - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \mathbf{q}^{B^{II}} + e^{-i\theta(\overline{\lambda_{II}}-1)} \overline{\mathbf{B}^B} [\mathbf{I} - (\overline{\lambda_{II}} - 1)(1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^*] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{B^{II}}} \quad (62)$$

$$\Pi_i^{II}(\theta) = e^{i\theta\lambda_{II}} \mathbf{A}^B \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{II}} \mathbf{I} - (1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^* \right] \mathbf{q}^{B^{II}} + e^{-i\theta\overline{\lambda_{II}}} \overline{\mathbf{A}^B} \left[\frac{1}{\lambda_{II}} \mathbf{I} - (1 - e^{-2i\theta}) \mathbf{Q}^* \right] \overline{\mathbf{q}^{B^{II}}} \quad (63)$$

The only quantities in Eqs. (50) and (51) that are not obtained from the asymptotic analysis are the mode I and mode II stress intensities K_I^n and K_{II}^n which depend on the specific far-field geometry and loading of the solid.

CALCAULATION OF STRESS INTENSITIES WITH THE H-INTEGRAL

The path independent H -integral is based on the application of Betti's reciprocal work theorem to the interface corner geometry. Betti's reciprocal work theorem is based on two sets of elastic fields: the actual and the complementary. In the absence of body forces, the H -integral takes a form (see Fig. 1):

$$H = \int_{\Gamma} (\sigma_{ij} u_i^* - \sigma_{ij}^* u_i) n_j ds = 0. \quad (64)$$

Here σ_{ij} and u_i are the actual stresses and displacements. These can be obtained either analytically or, more practically, from a finite element and boundary element analysis. σ_{ij}^* and u_i^* are the complementary fields that satisfy the same equilibrium and constitutive relations as the actual fields, and n_j is the unit outward normal to the counter-clockwise contour Γ . The value of H taken along any closed contour not containing a singularity is zero. To determine K_I^n , we evaluate H using the mode I complementary fields and to determine K_{II}^n , we evaluate H using the mode II complementary fields.

If λ is an eigenvalue, then so is $-\lambda$, so we choose the complementary solution to be given by Eqs. (50)-(63) with eigenvalue $\lambda^* = -\lambda$. For calculating $K_I^{n^*}$, we can choose complimentary fields as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij}^{IM^*} = K_I^{n^*} r^{-\lambda_I-1} \Sigma_{ij}^{IM^*}(\theta) \quad (65)$$

$$u_i^{IM^*} = K_I^{n^*} r^{-\lambda_I} \Pi_i^{IM^*}(\theta). \quad (66)$$

In the case of $K_{II}^{n^*}$, we can choose complimentary fields as follows:

$$\sigma_{ij}^{IIM^*} = K_{II}^{n^*} r^{-\lambda_{II}-1} \Sigma_{ij}^{IIM^*}(\theta) \quad (67)$$

$$u_i^{IIM^*} = K_{II}^{n^*} r^{-\lambda_{II}} \Pi_i^{IIM^*}(\theta). \quad (68)$$

For both modes, $\Sigma_{ij}^*(\theta)$ and $\Pi_i^*(\theta)$ are determined in the same way $\Sigma_{ij}(\theta)$ and $\Pi_i(\theta)$ were determined. The only unknowns in Eqs. (65)-(68) are then the mode I and mode II complementary scaling factors, $K_I^{n^*}$ and $K_{II}^{n^*}$. For mode I loading of the interface corner, we obtain the scaling factor $K_I^{n^*}$ by setting $H = H_I = K_I^{n^*}$ and evaluating the integral in Eq. (64) along an arc a distance r from the tip of the interface corner that extends from the lower face to the upper face as shown in Fig. 1, using the asymptotic solution for σ_{ij} and u_i of Eq. (64). Explicitly, this is written in polar coordinates as

$$H = H_I = \int_{-\beta}^{\alpha} (\sigma_{rr} u_r^{I^*} + \sigma_{\theta\theta} u_{\theta}^{I^*} - \sigma_{r\theta}^* u_r - \sigma_{r\theta}^* u_{\theta}) r d\theta = \int_{-\beta}^{\alpha} (\sum_{i,j=1}^2 n_i \sigma_{ij} u_j^{I^*} - n_i \sigma_{ij}^* u_j) r d\theta = K_I^{n^*} \quad (69)$$

where $n_1 = \cos\theta$ and $n_2 = \sin\theta$. We can obtain the mode I scaling factor $K_I^{n^*}$ as follows:

$$K_I^{n^*} = 1 / \left\{ \int_{-\beta}^{\alpha} (\sum_{i,j=1}^2 n_i \Sigma_{ij}^I \Pi_j^{I^*} - n_i \Sigma_{ij}^{I^*} \Pi_j^I) d\theta \right\}. \quad (70)$$

The same procedure is used to obtain the mode II scaling factor $K_{II}^{n^*}$ by setting $H = H_{II} = K_{II}^{n^*}$ and evaluating the integral in Eq. (64). The mode II scaling factor $K_{II}^{n^*}$ is obtained as follows:

$$K_{II}^{n^*} = 1 / \left\{ \int_{-\beta}^{\alpha} (\sum_{i,j=1}^2 n_i \Sigma_{ij}^{II} \Pi_j^{II^*} - n_i \Sigma_{ij}^{II^*} \Pi_j^{II}) d\theta \right\}. \quad (71)$$

With this choice for the complementary fields, the H -integral can be readily evaluated for an arbitrary bi-material interface corner by computing σ_{ij} and u_i using the finite element method. Here we use the finite element analysis results to evaluate the H -integral for a specific

geometry and load configuration. We choose the contour which passes through the element Gauss points because we have a better representation of the stresses at these points. However, we must interpolate the displacements to these points. Finally, we can obtain the stress intensities as follows:

$$K_I^n = \int_{-\beta}^{\alpha} \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^2 n_i \sigma_{ij} u_j^{I*} - n_i \sigma_{ij}^{I*} u_j \right) r d\theta \quad (72)$$

$$K_{II}^n = \int_{-\beta}^{\alpha} \left(\sum_{i,j=1}^2 n_i \sigma_{ij} u_j^{II*} - n_i \sigma_{ij}^{II*} u_j \right) r d\theta \quad (73)$$

where σ_{ij}^{I*} , u_i^{I*} , σ_{ij}^{II*} , and u_i^{II*} are calculated from Eqs. (65)-(68). σ_{ij} and u_i are obtained from the finite element analysis results.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a procedure for getting eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors of anisotropic/isotropic bi-materials with a notch was developed using the expanded Stroh formalism, which gave simpler procedure than before for obtaining eigenvalue problems. The solution for the displacement fields of the isotropic material, which should be used in calculating the H-integral, was appended to the expanded Stroh formalism. An example of co-cured double lap joint with composite and steel adherends was presented to help understand the procedure. Using the eigenvalues and associated eigenvectors asymptotic stress and deformation fields were given for singular points of the bonded joint. For calculation of stress intensities the H-integral, which had been derived from the Reciprocal Work Contour Integral Method (RWCIM), was used. Complementary fields with eigenvalue $\lambda^* = -\lambda$ were chosen to calculate the mode I and mode II complementary scaling factors, K_I^{n*} and K_{II}^{n*} , respectively. Finally, stress intensities could be calculated using finite element analysis results to evaluate the H-integral for a specific geometry and load configuration.

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